

Thesis for the Degree of Master of Science in Construction Management

**Assessment of Preparedness and Awareness on Fire Safety among
Management, Occupants and Concerned Authority of Selected
Commercial Buildings at Birtamode, Jhapa**

Shangrila Lama

(2019-1-06-0027)

School of Engineering

Faculty of Science and Technology

Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal

Joint Constituent College of Pokhara University,

Urlabari -3, Morang

November, 2021

Thesis for the Degree of Master of Science in Construction Management

**Assessment of Preparedness and Awareness on Fire Safety among
Management, Occupants and Concerned Authority of Selected
Commercial Buildings at Birtamode, Jhapa**

Supervised by

Assoc. Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D.

A thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree
of Master of Science in Construction Management

Shangrila Lama

(2019-1-06-0027)

School of Engineering

Faculty of Science and Technology

Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal

Joint Constituent College of Pokhara University,

Urlabari -3, Morang

November, 2021

Declaration

I hereby declare that this study entitled “**Assessment of Preparedness and awareness on fire safety among management, occupants and concerned authority of Selected Commercial Buildings at Birtamode, Jhapa**” is based on my original research work. Related works on the topic by other researchers have been duly acknowledged. I owe all the liabilities relating to the accuracy and authenticity of the data and any other information included here under.

Signature:

Name of Student: Shangrila Lama

P.U. Registration Number: 2019-1-06-0027

Date: November, 2021

Recommendation

This is to certify that this thesis entitled “**Assessment of Preparedness and awareness on fire safety among management, occupants and concerned authority of Selected Commercial Buildings at Birtamode, Jhapa**” prepared and submitted by **Shangrila Lama**, in partial fulfillment of the requirements of the degree of Master of Science (M.Sc.) in Construction Management awarded by Pokhara University, has been completed under my supervision. I recommend the same for acceptance by Pokhara University.

Signature:

Name of Supervisor: Assoc. Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D.

Organization: Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal

Designation: Research Director

Date: November, 2021

Acknowledgements

First and foremost, I'd like to express my heartfelt gratitude to my thesis supervisor, Assoc. Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D., Research Director of MBRC, for his unwavering support and appreciation for my master's study and research, as well as their patience, motivation, enthusiasm.

I would like to thank managing director of one stop mall, Mr. Mijas Pokhrel and manager of Hanuman Central, chief of firefighting Birtamode Municipality for their cooperation towards my research and helping me to complete the questionnaire of my research.

Last but not the least; I would like to thank all my Classmates, especially to Er, sujan khadka for his immense support and help throughout my research and also to all my family members, my wife for their emotional and mental support during my research.

Signature:

Name of Student: Shangrila Lama

P.U. Registration Number: 2019-1-06-0027

Date: November, 2021

Abstract

The study was carried out to analyze the current fire safety status of existing commercial buildings, preparedness and awareness among the management, occupants and concerned authority of selected commercial buildings at Birtamode, Jhapa and prepare the tentative cost of additional tools and equipment's needed. This research is focused on two commercial buildings; Hanuman central and One stop mall (Birtamode Jhapa). These building are selected for research as both of the buildings are considered as largest shopping malls and they also vary in planning and construction technology.

Standard fire safety status check was done with comparing with NBC 107:1994. A standard check list was prepared and compared with current status of buildings. Then fire safety preparedness and awareness of management, occupants were analyzed. After then preparedness and awareness of concerned authority like fire fighters, Municipality and Nepal police were analyzed. Data was collected from occupants, management and concerned authority based on the questionnaires survey, site visits with check list and key informant interview. Information regarding fire safety preparedness and awareness was presented in tabular form, charts and Key informants interview and questionnaire.

During survey of the existing commercial building it was found that not all the guideline mentioned in NBC 107: 1994 was followed. Many aspects of door detailing and stairs detailing were considered in Hanuman Central whereas in case of one stop mall staircase was narrow. Design aspect of Hanuman Central was found more advanced. There was four Exit route however only two of them lead to open space. One escape route lead to basement parking and another was behind the building from where street was nearly 300m far. Semi enclosed stairs were present in all four buildings. No proper signage of exit was found. One stop mall seems to be more prepared and concerned about the fire safety. Smoke detector, dry powder extinguishers was found in working condition. Water hose reel was installed but was not functional as water tank was not operational and also lack of trained manpower was main problem there. It had four exit, two staircase and two escalators.

Most of the occupants were not prepared for fire safety. Occupants were found unaware on building features, emergency evacuation procedure and firefighting equipment's operation. Management seems to be more focused on financial aspect rather than safety. Lack of proper firefighting equipment's, equipment's in poor condition, unmanaged electrical wires is the existing problem in the buildings. Concerned authority (Birtamode Municipality) had a fire Fighting team with a six fire men with a tank and fire fighting vehicle. But the new technologies like GPS were not introduced to firefighter. There were many cases reported where due to lack of communication gap between the fire fighter and residents, the response was late which resulted more damage. Lack of fire hydrant near the major commercial buildings created problem for fire fighter to refill their water tank. Narrow roads inside the municipality, poor implementation of fire safety code were major problem for fire fighters. The tentative cost for the installation of fire safety tools and equipment's Rs 5, 15,000 and Rs 9, 50,000 for one stop mall and Hanuman central respectively.

Keywords: fire safety, management, occupants, concerned authority, NBC 107: 1994, preparedness and awareness, fire extinguisher, water hose reels.

Table of Content

Declaration	iii
Recommendation	iv
Certificate	v
Acknowledgements	vi
Abstract	vii
Table of Contents	viii
List of Figures	xi
List of Tables	xii
Abbreviation/Acronyms	xiii
CHAPTER-I: INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Background	1
1.2 Statement of Problem	3
1.3 Research Questions	4
1.4 Research Objectives	5
1.5 Significance of the Study	5
1.6 Scope and Limitations	5
1.6.1 Scope	5
1.6.2 Limitation	5
CHAPTER-II: LITERATURE REVIEW	6
2.1 Fire	6
2.2 Classes of Fire	6
2.3 Fire in Buildings	6
2.3.1 The chemistry of fire	6
2.4 Principles of Fire Spread in a Building	7
2.4.1 Convection	8
2.4.2 Conduction	8
2.4.3 Radiation	9
2.5 Fire Protection In Buildings	9
2.5.1 Passive Fire Protection	10
2.5.2 Active Fire Protection	10
2.6 Hazard Control	13

2.7	Fire Safety Preparedness	14
2.8	Fire Safety Management	14
2.8.1	Fire Safety Management Roles and Responsibilities	15
2.9	Fire Safety Code	15
2.9.1	NepalNationalBuildingCodeNBC107:1994	15
CHAPTER-III: METHODOLOGY		17
3.1	Research Design	17
3.2	Research Approach	18
3.3	Study Area	18
3.3.1	Study Population	19
3.3.2	Sample Size	19
3.4	Data Collection	20
3.4.1	Primary Data Collection	20
3.4.2	Secondary Data Collection	20
3.5	Data Analysis	20
CHAPTER-IV: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION		20
4.1	Comparison Of In Field Fire Safety Status With NBC 107:1994	22
4.1.1	Hanuman Central	26
4.2	Observation detail	36
4.3	Fire Safety Preparedness of Management, Occupants and Concerned Authority	36
4.3.1	Awareness and Preparedness of Occupants on Fire Safety One Stop Mall and Hanuman Central Birtamode	36
4.3.2	Awareness and preparedness of Management on fire safety for One Stop Mall and Hanuman Central	42
4.3.3	Awareness and preparedness of concerned authority on fire safety of One Stop Mall and Hanuman Central Birtamode	43
CHAPTER-V: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS		45
5.1	Key Findings	45
5.2	Conclusions	47
5.3	Recommendation	53
5.4	Recommendation for further research work	49

REFERENCES	50
APPENDICES	52
Appendix 1: Questionnaire for Fire Experts in Local Authority	52
Appendix 2: Emergency Egress Questionnaire	53
Appendix 3: Observation Chart	55
Appendix 4: Responses of Questionnaire by Occupants of Selected Commercial Building	56
Appendix 5: Responses of Questionnaire by Management of One Stop Mall	57
Appendix 6: Responses of Questionnaire by Management of Hanuman Central	58
Appendix 7: Responses of Questionnaire by Fire Brigade Birtamode Municipality	59

List of Figures

Title	Page
Figure2.1: Triangle of Fire	7
Figure2.2: Smoke spread: Convection	8
Figure2.3: Fire spread: Convection	8
Figure2.4: Fire spread: Radiation	9
Figure2. 5: Interaction between Active and Passive Fire Protection Measures	10
Figure2.6: Hazard Control Hierarchy	13
Figure3.1: Conceptualization of Research Design	17
Figure3.2: Research Design	17
Figure4.1: Floor plan with exit of One stop mall	24
Figure4.2: Ground Floor Plan (Semi basement) Hanuman central	28
Figure4.3: Ground floor plan (Hanuman Central	29
Figure4.4: Plan with escape routes (Hanuman Central)	29
Figure4.5: Awareness of Building Feature	37
Figure4.6: Awareness of Emergency Egress	39
Figure4.7: Awareness on Assistance	40
Figure4.8: Ability to operate Fire Safety Equipments	42

List of tables

Title	Page
Table 1.1 Damage and loss due to Fire: 2021	2
Table 3.2 Summary of methodology	20
Table 4.1: Comparison of NBC107: 1994 with Selected Commercial Buildings	23
Table 4.2: Compliance Status of NBC:107, One Stop Mall	25
Table 4.3: Compliance Status of NBC:107; Hanuman Central For (Semi Basement)	30
Table 4.4: Compliance Status of NBC:107; Hanuman Central for Ground Floor	31
Table 4.5: Observational Detail	36
Table 4.6: Awareness on building feature	36
Table 4.7 Awareness of Emergency Egress	38
Table 4.8 Provision of Assistance	39
Table 4.9 Awareness on Fire Safety Measures	41
Table 4.10 Ability to Operate Fire Safety Equipment	41
Table4.11 Cost estimate For One Stop Mall	43
Table 4.12 Cost estimate For Hanuman central	44

Abbreviation/Acronyms

CCTV	Closed-Circuit Television
FFS	Fire Fighting System
GoI	Government of India
GoN	Government of Nepal
IFC	International Fire Code
IS	Indian Standards
KII	Key Informant Interview
NBC	Nepal Building Code
NNBC	Nepal National Building Code
PPE	Personal Protection Equipment
MBMAN	Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal
OSHA	Occupational Safety and Health Administration
UNDP	United Nation Development Program
ICC	International Code Council
BM:-	Birtamode Municipality

CHAPTER-I: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Fire is the exothermic chemical process of combustion in which a substance is rapidly oxidized, releasing heat, light, and a variety of reactive chemicals. Accidents, deliberate igniting, and equipment failure are all possible causes of fire. In today's electronic environment, fires caused by malfunctioning electrical equipment and power distribution systems are on the rise. Electrical fires are caused by faulty, modified, or unapproved electrical equipment, as well as damaged electrical conductors, plug wires, or extension cables (Ogajo, 2013).

One of the most common causes of damage in commercial buildings is that residents are believed to be somewhat, if not completely, unfamiliar with the structure. The inhabitants are anticipated to be mobile and capable of self-preservation, but may have difficulty discovering and walking to exits in an emergency due to crowding and unfamiliarity. In addition, the display of merchandise can have a higher fire growth rate than other types of businesses (International code council, 2009).

Due to rapid urbanization and haphazard development, there is more probability of fire in urban areas. In recent years electricity has been recognized as main source of fire. Firefighting also have been main challenge for fire fighters due to lack of access of water, lack of water hydrant, lack of awareness and knowledge, narrow roads, miscommunication etc. According to the United Nations Development Program, the most common causes of fire in Nepal are blackout induced fires caused by house owners' negligence, blackout induced fires caused by accident caused by burning candles, fire was aggravated because access for firefighting vehicles was blocked due to vehicle parking, motorbikes, and street vendors, and electrical short circuits.

Smoke and toxic gases are produced by fire and can be deadly to people who are exposed to them. As a result, there is a need for fire prevention and protection. It is accomplished by delaying the start of the fire to give people more time to flee and for the fire department to arrive at the scene. (Ogajo, 2013).

Fire damage causes damage of occupant's life, structural damage and loss of properties (Sun, 2013). A fire disaster will result in not only property destruction but also life-threatening situations. As a result, extreme caution must be exercised when working with components that have a high danger of igniting a fire (Yatims, 2009).

Table 1. 1 Damage and loss due to Fire: 2021

No. of death	No. of person injured	No. of house damaged	No. of affected family	No. of incidents
457	1758	11491	18760	12635

(Source: Government of Nepal, Ministry of Home Affairs, 2021)

Fire prevention is a matter of being aware of the factor which causes fire to start, then taking steps to prevent. It need a program of education and supervision of work force, a plan for proper and regular maintenance of plant and equipment and proper location of firefighting equipment which also need to be kept maintain and provided unobstructed access (Derek,1986).

In July 27, 2019 Fire erupted in Hanuman Central at Birtamode which incurred loss of 20 million. The building caught a flame due to short circuit in an air conditioner machine of shoe shopon ground floor of six storey building.

Plate 1.1: - fire news on nagarik daily about Hanuman central

A few months back fire erupted in Sri Krishna market which incurred loss of 15 million. Fire was started from an electronic shop go down around 1:00 – 2:00 am and was taken under control only in 7 am in the morning. Fire fighters from Birtamode Municipality and Mechinagar Municipality along with Nepali Army were able to control the fire.

Plate 1.2: - Fire at Namaste Ply indsurty at chaitubari, Birtamode -2 (RSS)

(<https://thehimalayantimes.com/nepal/fire-guts-plywood-factory-in-jhapa>)

In Dec 4, 2020 A huge fire broke out at the Namaste Ply Industry at Chaitubari, Birtamod-2 in Jhapa district and gutted property worth Rs 3 million. According to Deputy Superintendent of Police of District Police Office Jhapa, Rakesh Thapa, a short circuit led to the fire. As police received the information, a joint team constituting the Area Police Office Anarmani, the Province 1 Disaster Management Company Chandragadhi and the Armed Police Force Base Camp Sanischare went for the rescue. Locals and security personnel worked together to douse the fire using fire engines from Damak, Bhadrapur and Birtamod.

In case of Nepal, Safety seems to be of less priority either in design or in operational phase. Owner doesn't seem to be aware and prepared of unforeseen situation. Concerned authority seems weak in implementing the fire safety awareness and fire safety code. NBC Fire code has become just a document. This research mainly focuses on current fire safety condition existing commercial building and awareness and preparedness of management, occupants and concerned authority and prepare a tentative budget for installation of fire safety tools and equipment's.

The study area is one stop mall and Hanuman Central located at Birtamode, Jhapa, Nepal

1.2 Statement of Problem

When a building catches fire, the spread of the fire is mostly determined by the basic flammability of the building materials and contents, as well as the structure's architecture. The less time residents have to evacuate a burning structure, the faster it burns. As a result, commercial complex needs higher fire safety (Mehaffey, 1987).

If a fire breaks out, it is important that residents are made aware of the situation as quickly as possible and are aware of the steps they must take to go to a safer area. In addition to the safety of those within a burning structure, the protection of those in nearby buildings is

equally critical (Malhotra, 1993).

Due to fire hazards, large amount of property and thousands of life are directly and indirectly affected every year in Nepal. As Nepal being a Developing nation, undergoing and completed projects under government fund seem to be lacking the safety principles. Safety is a less priority to both the party Employer and the contractor. Although the NBC 107-1994 has addressed about fire safety but it doesn't seems to be adequate.

Design of Modern Malls and complex in Urban Areas seem to consider the fire safety in some manner. But the available facility and measures are more like a formality for owners. Date expired extinguisher, lack of emergency exit, poor design, more commercial space than flowing space, owners motive of profit maximization, lack of awareness, lack of electrical drawings, poor electrical connection, low quality electrical material, unmanaged use of electrical appliances due to weather, less knowledge on fire safety, etc. are the major issues seen.

As the development works are rapidly increasing day by day fire safety should become a topic to be considered. OHS should be given first priority by concerned authority and management.

Although firefighting is top priority for management in big metropolitan city like Kathmandu(capital city of Nepal) and Pokhara, newly emerged city like Damak, Biratnagar, Birtamode are seems to be unaware and negligent in this topic. Management, concerned authority and occupants are also seems to be unaware on this topic and fire has been kept on the least priority by them. Firefighting preparedness is not a priority for government compared to earthquake (UNDP, 2009). Fire safety code was formulated in 1994 A.D. and after then it has just became a piece of document and also was never revised till now. Even, UNDP has stated the need for modern and up-to-date fire code. Since NBC 107:1994 is not a technical but also a legal document, it needs to be updated based on changing circumstances to ensure fire safety. So the researcher has selected two commercial building and assessed fire safety in terms of awareness and preparedness of Management, Concerned authority and Occupants and also calculated the tentative cost of installation of fire safety tools and equipment's in the buildings.

1.3 Research Questions

Following question are designed as the research question.

- i. What is the compliance status of fire safety based on NBC 107: 1994 of selected commercial building of Birtamode, Jhapa?
- ii. What is the status of awareness and preparedness of management, concerned authority and occupants?
- iii. What will be the cost of installation of fire safety tools and equipment's?

1.4 Research Objectives

The overall objective of research is Assessment of Preparedness and Awareness on Fire Safety among Management, Occupants and Concerned Authority of Selected Commercial Buildings at Birtamode, Jhapa

The specific objectives are

- iv. To assess the current fire safety condition.
- v. To evaluate the level of awareness and preparedness of management Concerned authority and Occupants.
- vi. To analyze the cost of adding fire safety tools and equipment's.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The research is crucial for concerned authorities and occupants to understand the current state of fire safety in commercial buildings. It can be helpful for the management about the cost of additional fire safety tools and equipment's that can be quickly installed. It can be helpful for new Designers and Developers about the fire safety practice and importance of it in case of emergency. It can be important document for all three parties for increasing their awareness and preparedness in case of emergency.

1.6 Scope and Limitations

1.6.1 Scope

The building fire safety condition was checked comparing with NBC 107: 1994 only. A standard checklist was prepared and fire safety status was checked through field observation. Awareness and preparedness of all the parties was done through questionnaire.

1.6.2 Limitation

The study only looked at the existing state of fire safety, and it was confined to an investigation of the components of escape routes, such as the staircase, corridor, fire door, and intermediate floor.

As the research is performed on existing building the recommendation and solution might be less as compared to newly designed.

CHAPTER-II: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Fire

Fires occur when a flammable or combustible material, in combination with an adequate volume of an oxidizer such as oxygen gas or another oxygen-rich compound (though non-oxygen oxidizers exist that can replace oxygen), is exposed to a source of heat or ambient temperature above the fuel/oxidizer mix's flash point, and is able to sustain a rate of rapid oxidation that produces a chain reaction (Mishra and Shrestha 2017).

2.2 Classes of Fire

Based on the kind of fuel that is burning, fire is classified as follows. This classification system supports in the identification of threats and the selection of the most effective extinguishing agent.

Class A: - It involves common flammable materials: wood, paper, and fabric fires are generally slow in nature, and because they are solids, they are easier to eliminate.

Class B: - Gasoline, fuel oil, and propane are among the flammable and combustible liquids and gases found there. They progress and expand at a rapid speed. The fluid nature of these materials allows them to flow and move. Managing these materials is tough.

Class C: - It includes motors, appliances, and machinery that are powered by electricity. This fire classification has nothing to do with the type of fuel. The fire is no longer classified as Class C after it has been controlled.

Class D: - Combustible metals such as magnesium, titanium, and zirconium are involved. These materials are typically difficult to ignite, but once ignited, they produce large fires. Class D fires are extremely difficult to put out, yet they are quite rare in nature.

Class K: - It has to do with cooking oils. This is the most recent course.

2.3 Fire in Buildings

The study of fire science has provided insight into the mechanisms of ignition, fire growth, and fire spread, as well as the issues of smoke mobility and toxicity. An understanding of the function of fire science in ensuring fire safety in buildings was gained by considering the crucial stages of a fire in a room or compartment of a building (Mishra and Shrestha 2017).

2.3.1 The chemistry of fire

The combination of fuel and oxygen, as well as the application of enough heat to achieve ignition, results in a chemical reaction (Yatims, 2009). The fire triangle describes the chemistry of fire.

a) The fire triangle

The 'fire triangle' is a basic illustration of the three elements required to start a fire. All materials can be made to burn if given enough heat to allow the molecules to break down and release vapor. When the vapor or gas is released, it ignites, causing more heat to be released, and the fire propagation process begins. The material that remains after a fire has decomposed has less ability to react, leading the fire to die down and go out. (Mishra and Shrestha 2017)

Fire is a chemical reaction requiring:

- Heat (an ignition source)
- Fuel (gas, flammable liquid, timber)
- Oxygen (air)

Figure 2. 1: Triangle of Fire (Source: Furness & Muckett, 2007)

b) Fire Reaction

If Propane (C₃H₈) is the fuel the reaction is:

Complete Combustion

2

2

Incomplete Combustion

2.4 Principles of Fire Spread in a Building

There are three methods for a fire to spread within a building once it has begun and there is enough fuel and oxygen to keep it going:

- convection

- conduction and
- radiation

2.4.1 Convection

The most typical way for a fire to spread within a building or structure is through convection. Hot gases and smoke air will rise vertically through stairwells, lift shaft risers to the highest level available, and then create a layer at that height, from where they will spread out horizontally until checked. As a fire burns, significant amounts of smoke are produced, which normally spreads ahead of the flames, quickly filling a building. Smoke also reduces vision and obscures escape routes, causing panic and disorientation, which reduces the chances of a successful escape.

Figure 2. 2: Smoke spread: Convection(Source: Furness & Muckett,2007)

2.4.2 Conduction

The movement of heat through a material is known as conduction. The ability of conductors to carry heat varies greatly depending on the substance they are made of. Metal, for example, is a far better conductor than masonry. Conduction can occur in solids, liquids, or gases, but it is most common in solids when it comes to flames in buildings. (Furness & Muckett, 2007).

Figure 2. 3 Fire spread: Convection(Source: Furness & Muckett,2007)

2.4.3 Radiation

Figure 2.4 Fire Spread: Radiation (Source: Furness & Muckett, 2007)

Radiation is the transmission of thermal energy in the form of electromagnetic waves that heat solids and liquids (but not gases) in their path. Fires can spread to combustible things left to dry, or from building to building, when heat from a fire is radiated to a neighboring structure through windows, igniting combustible materials in the second building, as in the case of a heater or open fire.

2.5 Fire Protection In Buildings

The study and practice of minimizing the negative consequences of potentially destructive fires is known as fire protection. It entails research and development, production, testing, and deployment of mitigating devices, as well as the study of the behavior, compartmentalization, suppression, and investigation of fire and related emergencies (Grant cited by Ogajo, 2013). Before the environment becomes dangerous, it is critical to provide a chance for the residents to move to a safe location, either inside or outside the building (Sagun, 2013).

Passive and active protections are two major categories of methods that will safeguard people in the case of a fire (Furness & Muckett, 2007).

In a building, passive measures like as non-combustible material selection, building subdivision, and proper ventilation are present and operating at all times. Active measures include upgrades to a building's services, such as the installation of alarms and detectors. (Mugure cited by Ogajo, 2013).

Figure 2. 5: Interaction between Active and Passive Fire Protection Measures

(Source: Ogajo, 2013)

2.5.1 Passive Fire Protection

The principle of suppression underpins passive fire prevention. The building's compartments are designed in such a way that they can only be used in one location. Fire doors, for example, should keep smoke and flames out of lobbies, stairwells, and lift shafts. The design of escape pathways, which should not include combustible wall, ceiling, or floor linings, is another form of passive fire prevention. Where ducts pass through compartment walls, fire dampers should be fitted, as well as gaps in such walls around cables (Furness & Muckett, 2007).

A continuous and uninterrupted line of exit travel from any point within a workplace to a safe location is known as an exit route. Exit access, exit, and exit discharge are the three parts of an exit route. Exit access refers to a section of an exit route that leads to an exit. The term "exit" refers to a section of an exit route that is normally segregated from other regions in order to offer a safe approach to the exit discharge. Escape discharge is a section of the exit route that leads immediately outdoors or to a roadway, promenade, refuge place, public way, or open space having outside access (OSHO a).

2.5.2 Active Fire Protection

Active fire suppression systems can either detect or extinguish a fire, with a water sprinkler or inert gas flooding system providing both duties. In the early stages of a fire, an automatic fire detection system will detect heat or combustion products and sound the alarm (Furness & Muckett, 2007).

Fixed Firefighting Systems

A building's active protection is provided by fixed firefighting systems (FFS). Provision for FFS can be a compensating element during the design stage to provide additional protection to a wide space or susceptible part of a building (Furness & Muckett, 2007).

The most common FFS are:

- Automatic water sprinklers
- Drencher systems
- Flooding and inerting systems
- Water mist systems.
- Alarm Systems
- Smoke and Heat Detector
- Water hose reel

Automatic water sprinklers

Automatic water sprinkler systems will provide effective fire suppression in most portions of a building, ensuring safety.

- Fire detection at an early stage.
- By delivering water to the fire's heart, you can control its development, spread, heat, and smokeproduction.
- Operation of the local alarm system and validation of the alarm at the central control room.

➤ **Drenchers System**

Drencher systems are used to defend against radiated heat or to flood a high-risk process with water to ensure prompt and effective suppression. While a sprinkler system protects a building from interior fire, drenchers are installed on roofs, over windows and other external openings to protect the structure from damage caused by a fire in a nearby building.

➤ **Flooding and inerting systems**

Flooding and inerting systems work by flooding a specific extinguishing substance into a specific region. Different media, including as dry powder and various gases, are used in these systems. Flooding systems can be used to flood an entire compartment or building, or they can be utilized to flood a fire risk's immediate region.

➤ **Water mist systems**

Because the heat generated by the fire quickly vaporizes the water mist spray droplets into steam, they may quickly extinguish huge fires in enclosed locations. Small fires that have not yet heated an enclosure or are in broad open spaces, on the other hand, cannot be effectively put out by water mist sprays unless they are physically within the spray's range (Furness & Muckett, 2007).

➤ **Water hose reels**

Water hose reels are made up of coils of hose that are held in place by a sturdy reel and frame. It could be hanging from the wall on hinged brackets or hidden behind attractive panels that fit the decor. They may have a valve for turning on the water supply, or they may be equipped with an automatic system controlled by the reels axle, which turns on the water supply when a few yards of hose have been used up. Depending on the taste or demand, certain hoses are equipped with a plain jet nozzle or a hybrid jet/spray nozzle (Ogajo, 2013).

➤ **Alarm Systems**

There are various types of alarm systems; they are generally intended to alert people of the need to leave the facility in the event of an emergency.

It may be necessary for someone in the facility to manually activate it, usually through the use of a pull station. The alarm would then sound alarm bells, horns, strobes, or other suitable auditory or visual alarm devices after being manually engaged.

Plate 2. 1 Fire alarm

(Source: Craig, 2002)

➤ **Smoke and Heat Detector**

Automatic detection refers to devices on the alarm system that detect the presence of fire, such as smoke and heat detectors. This system can also be set up as a strictly local alarm, in which audible or visual warning devices are activated throughout the facility without the need for an occupant to manually activate them.

Plate 2. 2 Heat detector and smoke detector (Source: Craig, 2002)

2.6 Hazard Control

Hazard control hierarchy is a system used in industry to reduce or eliminate hazardous

exposure. Several safety organizations support it as a widely acknowledged system. Managers in industry are taught this approach, which is then promoted as standard practice. .

The hazard control hierarchy consists of six major approaches to handling hazards.

- Eliminate
- Substitute
- Isolate
- Engineering controls
- Administrative controls
- Personal protective equipment

Figure 2. 6 Hazard Control Hierarchy

(Source: <https://www.osha.gov/shpguidelines/hazard-prevention.html>)

This strategy should start at the top and work its way down. In an ideal world, all risks would be fully removed. If deletion isn't possible or practical, which it usually isn't, substitution should be considered, and so on as the list progresses.

Elimination: altering a design to eliminate a hazard; for example, introducing mechanical lifting systems to eliminate the hazard of manual handling.

Substitution: use a less harmful substance or cut the system's energy consumption (e.g. lower the force, amperage, pressure, temperature, etc.)

Engineering Controls: Install ventilation systems, machine guarding, interlocks, and sound enclosures, among other engineering controls.

Administrative Controls: Safety signs, hazardous area markings, photo-luminescent signs, pedestrian walkway markings, warning sirens/lights, alarms, safety protocols, equipment inspections, access controls, safe working systems, tagging, and work licenses, among other administrative controls

Personal protective equipment (PPE): safety glasses, hearing protection, and face shields, safety harnesses and lanyards, respirators, and gloves (OSHA b).

2.7 Fire Safety Preparedness

Preparedness entails altering one's behavior in order to lessen the impact of disasters on individuals (Drabek, 1986). It is a continuous cycle of planning, managing, organizing, training, equipping, exercising, creating, evaluating, monitoring, and improving activities to ensure effective coordination and the enhancement of capabilities of concerned organizations in preventing, protecting against, responding to, recovering from, creating resources, and mitigating the effects of natural disasters, acts of terrorism, and other man-made disasters (Falkenrath cited by Ogajo, 2013).

During the preparedness phase, emergency managers create strategies to manage and mitigate their risks, as well as take steps to acquire the required capabilities to put those plans into effect.

Common preparedness measures include:

- Communication plans that use vocabulary and methods that are simple to understand.
- Emergency services should be properly maintained and trained.
- The creation and testing of emergency population warning systems, as well as emergency shelters and evacuation strategies.
- Establish and maintain an emergency communication system that can assist in determining the nature of an emergency and providing instructions as necessary (Ogajo, 2013).

2.8 Fire Safety Management

In terms of fire prevention and safety, management is critical. A building's fire safety design consists of a range of measures relating to the layout, structure, and other requirements, some of which are activated in the event of a fire (Malhotra, 1993).

Regular inspection, maintenance, posting of notices and exit directed signs, regular fire exercises, evacuation strategies, and the presence of fire wardens are all part of fire safety management (Ogajo, 2013).

The primary goal of fire safety management is to guarantee that all accessible fire safety

measures are available for individuals to use in order to aid their escape (Baker, 2003).

2.8.1 Fire Safety Management Roles and Responsibilities

In a business facility, pre-planned processes for dealing with a fire emergency are required. The roles and responsibilities of fire safety management are listed below.

Roles and Responsibilities

- Appoint a fire safety manager to ensure that fire safety protocols are followed and that maintenance needs are met. Ensure that staff is familiar with the safety procedures and the occupants carry out their work in a safe manner.
- A maintenance schedule should be developed for all fire detection/alarm systems, fire extinguishers, hose reels, and other similar items, and records of their inspection and repair should be preserved.
- Hold frequent fire drills for employees to ensure that they are aware of the proper means of escape, exit locations, and routes to take in the event of a fire.
- Make arrangements for evacuation, fire suppression, and aid to the fire department when they arrive. The strategy should be addressed with the fire department, and their agreement on the planned processes should be acquired (Malhotra, 2013).

2.9 Fire Safety Code

A building code is a rule or guideline that establishes the minimum standards for the design and construction of structures and buildings. The goal of establishing those basic requirements is to safeguard society's health and safety (Tzu-Sheng, 2013).

In new and existing buildings, structures, and processes, the fire safety code addresses fire prevention, fire protection, life safety, and the proper storage and use of hazardous materials. They give a comprehensive approach to hazard control in all structures and sites (International Code Council, 2009). The fire safety requirements for buildings were researched using NBC 107: 1994.

2.9.1 Nepal National Building Code NBC 107: 1994

Nepal national building code NBC 107:1994 provides fundamental requirements for fire safety in ordinary buildings (GoN, 1994). Summary of NBC 107: 1994 are listed below.

➤ Exit Requirement

A doorway, corridor, or passageway leading to an interior staircase, an outdoor staircase, a verandah going to the street, the roof of a building, or the street is considered an exit. The egress could perhaps lead to another structure in the area. The exit should

- Meet the minimum size criteria and enable for the evacuation of all people in a reasonable amount of time.
- Be devoid of any impediments and provide no resistance to movement.
- Be easily seen, especially with appropriate indicators.
- Be consistent and do not encroach on personal space.

➤ **Stairs**

- At least two fire escape staircases, one internal and the other external.
- When a building's plinth area reaches 500 m², more steps must be built in proportion to the increased plinth space.
- The minimum width is 1.5 meters.
- The distance between any point in a hallway and a building's stairway must not exceed 20 meters.

➤ **Fire Escapes**

- Every building with more than five stories must have a separate fire escape with a width of at least 75 cm.
- Each riser on the fire escape must be no more than 19 cm high and have a minimum tread width of 20 cm.
- The number of risers each flight must not exceed 15.
- This type of fire escape should lead users to an open area.

➤ **Exit Doors**

- Exit doors must open to a passageway or a corridor, but not to a passageway or a corridor, and they must open outwards without obstructing the movement of people passing outside the door.
- The maximum distance between any point in the route and such an exit doorway is 20 meters.
- The width and height of the exit doorway must not be less than 90 cm and 180 cm, respectively.

CHAPTER-III: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

Figure 3. 1: Conceptualization of Research Design

This is a pragmatic research where compliance status of fire safety has been assessed followed by awareness and preparedness along with tentative cost estimate assuring fire safety.

Research design was formulated as given in fig no 3.1 which can be made clearer with the help of flow diagram of fig 3.2

Figure 3. 2: Research Design

3.2 Research Approach

Both methodologies were used to conduct research (qualitative and quantitative). Direct interview, field observation, check list, discussion, and interaction with Management, Concerned Authority, and Occupants were used to gather primary data. Secondary data was gathered from a variety of sources, including journals, government papers such as NBC 107:1994, and other fire safety codes.

3.3 Study Area

To assess the awareness and preparedness of Management, concerned authority and occupants Buildings selected were one stop mall and Hanuman Central Birtamode.

One Stop Mall

One stop Mall is Located at Birtamode, Jhapa. It is located at North- west side from mukti chowk (Central part of Birtamode). The building, which is a shopping complex with six stories above ground, was finished in 2016. Three floors including the ground are used for shops and top three floors are used for Cinema purpose. Building is U-shaped with a large steel structure at front connecting to building. The structure has a variety of shops selling various goods and services, as well as leisure venues such as a movie, a game center, and a pub. Underground Parking Facility is also available but the building structural components don't have any connection with the parking below. Vertical circulation is assisted by escalators, elevators, and stairwells, while horizontal circulation is assisted by walkways and lobby.

Plate 3.1: - One stop mall

Hanuman Central

Hanuman central is also located at Birtamode, Jhapa touching national highway (Mahendra Highway). It is also known as Hanuman Complex. It was the first Commercial complex build in Birtamode. It was opened in 2012.

It is a Rectangular shaped building with atrium in the center. Vertical circulation is aided by elevators and stairwells, whereas horizontal circulation is aided by walkways and lobby. There are 3 staircases in the building with 3 elevators.

Plate 3.2: - Hanuman Central

3.3.1 Study Population

The study population consisted of the inhabitants of the selected commercial buildings, building management, and relevant authorities such as the Fire Department and Municipality. For conducting questionnaire survey, population was taken from the people of the study area. Both technical professionals and the users of the buildings in question were taken into account.

3.3.2 Sample Size

The Central Limit Theorem was used to calculate population size. The sample size for the One Stop Mall and Hanuman Central was 40, ensuring that each floor was represented.

3.4 Data Collection

The study collected both primary and secondary data.

3.4.1 Primary Data Collection

a) Questionnaire Survey

Based on the information from the literature review questionnaire was formulated. A survey of the occupants of selected business buildings was done. (See Appendix 1), management of selected commercial buildings (See Appendix 2), and concerned authority (See Appendix 3). It was conducted to understand fire safety awareness and preparedness of all three parties.

b) Key Informants Interview

Key informants interview was conducted with Head of management of Hanuman central and One stop mall, head of fire department(Birtamode Municipality) and Engineer of Birtamode Municipality(Building Department).

c) Observation

Selected study area was visited in order to analyze the current status of fire safety measures and to understand the compliance status of NBC 107:1994 in selected commercial buildings.

3.4.2 Secondary Data Collection

Secondary data was gathered from publications published in journals, conference papers, NBC 107:1994, IS 1644:1988, websites, and books, among other sources.

3.5 Data Analysis

After the data was collected, the following stage was to analyze the information. To achieve the first objective, data obtained after the survey and site visit was compared with NBC 107: 1994 with a check list. Similar to achieve second objective all three parties was interviewed, observation list was prepared and data were analyzed by qualitative method, occupant respond to the questionnaires were presented in tables and charts. For the last objective preparation of tentative cost estimation of fire safety tools and equipment's were calculated.

Table 3.1: Summary of Methodology

Objective	Activities	Analysis
1. To identify the current fire safety status of selected commercial buildings.	1. Checklist according to NBC107:1994 2. Site visit general check list	1. Qualitative Analysis
2. To identify the level of awareness among management, occupants and concerned authority.	1. Key Informant Interview 2. Questionnaire survey	1. Qualitative Analysis 2. Quantitative

		Analysis
3. To calculate the tentative cost of installation of fire safety tools and Equipment's.	1. Rate collection and calculation of cost.	1. Qualitative Analysis

CHAPTER-IV: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this chapter check list of general requirements of fire safety based on NBC 107: 1994 was prepared and visited to site.

4.1 Comparison Of In Field Fire Safety Status with NBC 107: 1994

Finding from the above mentioned codes has been compared and presented in the tabular form.

Table 4. 1: Comparison of NBC 107: 1994 with Selected Commercial Buildings

NBC 107: 1994	One Stop Mall	Hanuman Central
<p>EXIT</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. evacuation at short time 2. meet the minimum requirements of size 3. It must be free of any impediments and give noresistance to movement. 4. Clearly visible 5. Preferably with proper signs 6. It must be continuous andnot interrupt private space. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Every corner is 20feet away from staircase and escalator. 2. Yes, exit are wide enough (15' wide) 3. Yes 4. Yes 5. No signage wasfound. 6. 2 exit were open to street and 2 of them were open to private space(one building and one private street) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Hard for corner shop. 2. Exit leading to back of building and underground parking was found small but the front exit is wide enough. 3. Due to parking 2 of exit was obstructed and back exit was far from Open Street. 4. Exit were visible 5. No signage was found 6. Exit were open to own space but only front exit were directly open to street.
<p>STAIRCASE</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Min Width 1.5 m 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 1.2 m only 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. more than 1.5 m
<p>Travel distance</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Max 20 m 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 less than 20 m 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. less than 20m

<p>Exit door</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Open to a passageway or to the corridor Not less than 90cm width 180cm height Open outward 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> yes < 90cm < 180 cm 3 rolling shutters and one fully open 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> yes < 90cm < 180 cm two rolling shutters and two opening inward
<p>Fire escape or external stair</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Min width 75 cm tread 20 cm riser height 19 cm nos. of riser 15 carry user towards open space 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> < 75cm >20cm < 19cm > 15 yes 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> < 75cm = 20cm < 19cm > 15 two exit lead to underground parking and one lead to back of building
<p>Signs</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> be clearly visible, preferably with proper signs 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> No proper Signage 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> No proper Signage
<p>Firefighting equipment</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Dry riser Wet riser 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> No Yes (but not functional) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Yes (but not functional) no

4.1.1 One Stop Mall

Fig 4.1:- Floor plan with exit of One stop mall.

Table 4.3 : Compliance Status of NBC: 107, One Stop Mall

One stop mall	Exit1	Exit 2	Exit 3	Exit 4	Remarks
1. No. of exit					
2. Stair type					
Enclosed	Yes	No	No	No	Exit 1 Open to street connected with escalator
Open at street	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	
Door locks prohibited	NO	Yes	Yes	Yes	
3. Doorways					
Open to stair way	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
>= 100cm width	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	120 cm
>=200cm height	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	210 cm
Open outward	No	NO	No	No	
No Sliding and overhead door	Yes	No	No	No	
4. Fire escape					
Directly open to ground	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	
Free of obstruction all times	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	
5. Signs					
Proper signage	NO	No	No	No	
visible	No	NO	No	No	
illuminate	No	No	No	No	

Source: Field survey, 2021

Exit route 1 is located at south which is also a main entrance for building. It is connected with escalator. It opens to East-West Highway (Mahendra Highway). Exit no 2 is located at west which is connected to street 20' wide. Exit door is furnished with rolling shutter. Exit no 3 is located at north side of building and opens to small Private Street. Exit no 4 is also located at north side of building and opens to another building corridor. Management of One stop mall seems to be more prepared and aware about the fire safety. It also has a cinema hall in top 3 floor of the building that meets the standard of QFX cinemas. Cinema hall portion has smoke detector and alarm system but water sprinkle system was absent. The material used in wall and flooring of cinema hall was fire resistant

i.e. it can resist fire for 2-3 hours. Inside cinema hall there was proper signage placed at different places. Due to its architectural design every corner was closest to the staircase.

Staircase seems to be much smaller and narrower compared to standards. Water hydrant system is installed on both staircase but was not functional. Plenty of dry powder extinguishers can be seen in building. Exit route was found free from obstruction but the signage was missing.

Plate 4. 1: Firefighting equipment's

Plate 4. 2: - Fire Extinguisher and water hydrant inside cinema hall

Plate 4. 3: - Alarm system

Plate 4. 4: -Fire Detecting Board

Plate 4. 5:- Exit Connected with escalator Front Face

4.1.1 Hanuman Central

Hanuman central is G+5 storey building. It has 3 staircase, two elevators and 3 exit. It has basement with 1/3 portion underground parking facility. The middle of the complex has wide open space up to top and enough circulation space. Large central area is covered with truss and fully enclosed. For Semi Basement portion there are three entry and exit where two of them at front portion and one of them at back portion. For first floor there are two entrances at front and one at back.

Figure 4.2: - Ground Floor Plan (Semi basement)

Figure 4.3: - Ground floor plan

Figure 4.4: - Plan with escape routes

Table 4.3: Compliance Status of NBC: 107; Hanuman Central For (Semi Basement)

Hanuman Central	Exit 1	Exit 2	Exit 3	Remarks
1. No. of exit				3
2. Stair type				
Enclosed	No	No	No	
Open at street	Yes	Yes	No	
Door locks prohibited	Yes	Yes	Yes	
3. Doorways				
Open to stair way	NO	No	Yes	
>= 100cm width	Yes	Yes	Yes	120 cm
>=200cm height	Yes	Yes	Yes	210 cm
Open outward	-	-	-	
No Sliding and overhead door	-	-	-	
4. Handrail height				
Min100cm-max 120cm	Yes	Yes	Yes	100 cm
Gap between two vertical >=30cm and less than 15cm				Horizontal division provided
5. Fire escape				
Directly open to ground	Yes	Yes	No	open at ground floor and continuous to basement
Free of obstruction all times	Yes	Yes	Yes	
6. Signs				
Proper signage	No	NO	NO	
visible	No	No	No	
illuminate	No	No	No	

Source: Field survey, 2021

Exit no.1: was located at north side of building and opened to Street. Exit door was made up of rolling shutter. Exit no 2 was also located at north- east side of building which leads to semi basement parking. Due to parking the exit seems to be obstructed. Exit no 3 is located at south side of building leading to back portion of building. The door is connected to staircase. The travel distance from the door to open street is nearly 300 ft. There are 25 no's of fire extinguishers and also water hydrant system connected from semi basement to the top

of the building. There are multiple banks, cooperative bank, play station, food court, and Departmental store and so on.

Plate 4.6:- Exit door 2 with semi basement parking
3

Plate 4.7:- Exit door

Plate 4.8:- Exit Door 1

Table 4.4: Compliance Status of NBC: 107; Hanuman Central For Ground Floor

Hanuman Central	Exit 1	Exit 2	Exit 3	Remarks
1. No. of exit				3
2. Stair type				
Enclosed	No	No	No	
Open at street	No	Yes	No	
Door locks prohibited	Yes	Yes	Yes	
3. Doorways				
Open to stair way	NO	No	Yes	
>= 100cm width	Yes	Yes	Yes	120 cm

>=200cm height	Yes	Yes	Yes	210 cm
Open outward	-	-	-	
No Sliding and overhead door	-	-	-	
4. Handrail height				
Min100cm-max 120cm	Yes	Yes	Yes	100 cm
Gap between two vertical >=30cm and less than 15cm				Horizontal division provided
5. Fire escape				
Directly open to ground	Yes	Yes	No	open at ground floor and continuous to basement
Free of obstruction all times	Yes	Yes	Yes	
6. Signs				
Proper signage	No	NO	NO	
visible	No	No	No	
illuminate	No	No	No	

Source: Field survey, 2021

Exit no.1 and 2 are located at north side of building and opened to Street. Exit no 3 is located at south side of building leading to back portion of building. The door is connected to staircase. The travel distance from the exit 3 door to open street is nearly 300 ft.

Plate 4.9: - Entry/Exit 1 (Hanuman Central))

Plate 4.10:- Entry/Exit 2 (Hanuman Central)

Plate 4.11:- Entry/Exit door 3

Semi Basement

One third of Semi basement portion is used for parking and other part is used for commercial purpose. It has electric panel and transfer room, electric room, generator room and atrium at center. Generators which are source for heat smoke and toxic gases are kept at south-east side and also outside of building.

Plate 4.12: Water hydrant

Plate 4.13: - Generators at back of building.

Plate 4.14: - Parking at back part of building

Plate 4.15:- Fire extinguisher

Plate 4.16: - extinguishers on both side of elevators

Plate 4.17: - Unmanaged Electrical wiring

No any trained person was allocated for fire safety of building. The electrical wiring was seemed to be in unmanaged condition.

4.2 Observation detail

Table 4. 5: Observational Detail

Observation Detail	One Stop Mall		Hanuman Central	
	Exist	Do not exist	Exist	Do not Exist
Halon extinguishers	✓		✓	
Dry powder	✓		✓	
Carbon dioxide extinguishers		✓		✓
Sprinklers/Hose reels pressurized water extinguishers)	✓		✓	
Wet chemical		✓		✓
Fire blankets		✓		✓
Emergency communication system (alarm, telephone, mobile no. etc)	✓			✓
Emergency shelters for this building		✓		✓
Availability of an emergency fire disaster kit		✓		✓
Existence of Emergency population warning methods		✓		✓
Existence of a Fire hydrant		✓		✓
Open spaces for evacuation of people	✓		✓	
Existence of a Fire Assembly point		✓		✓

4.3 Fire Safety Preparedness of Management, Occupants and Concerned Authority.

The data from the questionnaire was used to create the graphs below, which show the inhabitants', management's, and concerned authority's level of fire safety readiness.

4.3.1 Awareness and Preparedness of Occupants on Fire Safety One Stop Mall and Hanuman Central Birtamode.

The table shows the level of fire safety readiness among the tenants of all chosen business buildings.

Table 4.6 Awareness on building feature

Awareness on building feature	Hanuman Central			One stop Mall		
	Yes	No	Can'tSay	Yes	No	Can'tSay
Building Design	10	12	18	20	19	1
Location of exit	28	11	1	27	13	0
Visibility of emergency sign	4	22	14	26	10	4

Respondents were asked to state whether or not they were aware of a certain building feature. The respondent's response is shown in Table 4.21. Ten Hanuman Central respondents were aware of the building design, 28 were aware of the position of the exit, and four respondents had emergency signs visible. 12 respondents were unfamiliar of the building layout, 11 were unaware of the position of the escape, and 22 respondents did not see an emergency sign. 18 respondents had no idea about the building plan, 1 had no information about the placement of the exit, and 14 had no idea about the emergency sign.

Figure 4. 5 Awareness of Building Feature

Twenty one-stop mall respondents were aware of the building design, 27 were aware of the position of the exit, and 26 respondents reported that emergency signs were visible. The building design was unknown to 19 respondents, the location of the exit was unknown to 13 respondents, and the emergency sign was not visible to ten respondents. One person had no idea about the building layout, 0 had no idea about the placement of the exit, and 4 had no idea about the emergency sign.

37.5% of respondents were aware about building Plan, 38.75% of respondents don't know about plan and 23.75 cannot say. 68.75% have knowledge about exit, 30% don't know and 1.25 cannot say about it, similarly 37.5% knows about emergency sign, 40% haven't seen and 22.5% cannot say about that.

Table 4. 7 Awareness of Emergency Egress

	Hanuman Central(nos. of occupants)			One stop mall (nos. of occupants)		
	Yes	No	Can'tSay	Yes	No	Can'tSay
Awareness on emergency Egress						
Emergency evacuation	20	18	2	22	7	11
Assembly point	12	16	12	14	20	6

20 respondents of Hanuman Central were aware about emergency evacuation, 12 respondents were aware about assembly point. 18 respondents were not aware emergency evacuation, 16 were unaware about assembly point. Whereas, 2 respondents had no idea about emergency evacuation, 12 respondents had no idea about assembly point.

22 respondents of LABIM Mall were aware about emergency evacuation, 14 respondents were aware about assembly point. 7 respondents were not aware about emergency evacuation, 20 were unaware about assembly point. Whereas, 11 respondents had no idea about emergency evacuation, 6 respondents had no idea about assembly point.

Figure 4. 6 Awareness

52.5% of respondents were found aware, 31.25% of respondents were not aware and 16.25% can't say about emergency evacuation. 32.5% were aware, 45% were aware and 22.5% can't say about Assembly point. Figure 4.5 show that occupants lacked awareness on emergency egress.

Management team should frequently organize regular fire drills to ensure that occupants remain aware of the appropriate means of escape and where they shall wait after emergency evacuation.

Table 4. 8 Provision of Assistance

Provision of assistance	Hanuman Central(nos. of occupants)			One Stop Mall (nos. of occupants)		
	Yes	No	Can't say	Yes	No	Can't say
Need emergency assistance	15	10	15	5	21	14
Assistance provided	7	17	16	8	12	20

15 respondents of Hanuman Central assumed they need assistance to reach place of safety, 12 respondents assumed assistance will be provided during fire emergency to reach place of safety. 10 respondents do not need assistance to reach place of safety, 17 respondents assumed assistance will not be provided during fire emergency to reach place of safety. Whereas, 15 respondents could not say if they needed assistance, and 16 respondents had no

idea if assistance would be provided during fire emergency.

5 respondents of One stop Mall needed assistance to reach place of safety, 8 respondents assumed assistance will be provided during fire emergency to reach place of safety. 21 respondents do not need assistance to reach place of safety, 12 respondents assumed assistance will not be provided during fire emergency to reach place of safety. Whereas, 14 respondents could not say if they needed assistance, and 20 respondents had no idea if assistance would be provided during fire emergency.

Figure 4. 7: Awareness on Assistance

25% of respondents required assistance to lead them to place of safety during fire emergency, 38.75% don't need any assistance and 36.25% occupants can't say about that. 18.75% assumed that assistance would be provided to during emergency, 36.25% of respondents think that assistance would not be provided during emergency and 45% can't say about that.

Table 4.9 Awareness on Fire Safety Measures

Fire safety Measures	Hanuman Central(nos. of occupants)			One Stop Mall (nos. of occupants)		
	Exist	Do not exist	Not sure	Exist	Do not exist	Not sure
Fire extinguisher	14	10	16	15	3	22
Water hose reel/water hydrant	10	12	18	12	10	18

Respondents of Hanuman Central were aware about the existence of fire extinguisher, 10 respondents were aware about the existence of water Hydrant in building. 10 respondents were unaware about the existence of fire extinguisher, 12 respondents were unaware about the existence of water hydrant and 16 respondents weren't aware about fire extinguisher, 18 respondents weren't aware about water hydrant.

Respondents of One stop were aware about the existence of fire extinguisher, 12 respondents were aware about the existence of water hose reel in building. 3 respondents were unaware about the existence of fire extinguisher, 10 respondents were unaware about the existence of water hose reel and 22 respondents weren't aware about fire extinguisher, 18 respondents weren't aware about water hose reel

Table 4. 10 Ability to Operate Fire Safety Equipment

Ability To Operate Fire Equipment	Hanuman Central(nos. of occupants)			One Stop Mall (nos. of occupants)		
	Able to	Notable to	Not sure	Able to	Notable to	Not sure
Fire extinguisher	10	22	8	13	18	9
Water hose reel/water hydrant	5	25	10	2	30	8

10 respondents of Hanuman Central think they were able to operate fire extinguisher, 5 respondents assumed they were able to operate water hose reel/water hydrant. 22 respondents were unable to operate fire extinguisher, 25 respondents were unable to operate water hose reel. Whereas, 8 respondents were not sure if they could operate fire extinguisher, 10 respondents were not sure if they could operate water hose reel.

13 respondents of One stop Mall assumed they were able to operate fire extinguisher, 2 respondents assumed they were able to operate water hose reel/water hydrant. 18 respondents were unable to operate fire extinguisher, 30 respondents were unable to operate water hose reel. Whereas, 9 respondents were not sure if they could operate fire extinguisher, 8 respondents were not sure if they could operate water hose reel/water hydrant.

Figure 4.8 Ability to operate Fire Safety Equipment's

28.75% of respondents were able to operate fire extinguisher, 50% of respondent were not able to operate and 21.25% were not sure. 8.75% were able to operate water hose reel / water hydrant, 68.75 were not able and 22.5% were not sure. Figure 4.9 shows that of occupants lacked ability to operate the firefighting equipment's. Therefore, proper training on shall be provided to the occupants frequently so that the loss during fire can be reduced.

4.3.2 Awareness and preparedness of Management on fire safety for One Stop Mall and Hanuman Central

For this step, direct interview was conducted with management. Management seems more focused on financial part of building. Fire extinguisher was only tool for fire safety. There was smoke detector and alarm system installed in One Stop Mall. Management of both the buildings have requested for installation of fire hydrant to Municipality many times. Water hydrant installed in both the building weren't in working condition. For detail refer to annex.

4.3.3 Awareness and preparedness of concerned authority on fire safety of One StopMall and Hanuman Central Birtamode.

Fire fighter of fire department of Birtamode had many problems regarding communication, training and information about new technology. Concerned authority (Birtamode Municipality) seems weak in implementation of code and law. They are not aware about the fire safety condition of existing commercial buildings. No any seminar or awareness program has been conducted by municipality for fire safety. Even the Municipality building didn't have proper sign for safe evacuation. Fire fighter seems always prepared but due to lack of direct communication they find hard to locate the site. Training for firefighter has been very often. Municipality seems just happy in collecting the fire tax while registration of new house. For detail refer to annex.

Table 4.11 Cost estimate For One Stop Mall

S.no	Description	No	Unit	Rate	Quantity	Remarks
1	Exit Signs and boards(Digital)	10	per piece	2500	25000	
2	Underground water tank for water hydrant (maintenance)	1	L/s	100000	100000	for functioning of existing watertank
3	Fire extinguisher (4.5 kg) CO2	5	per piece	12000	60000	
4	Fire Blanket	5	per piece	5000	25000	for each floor
5	Foam fire extinguisher	5	per piece	5000	25000	for each floor
6	Smoke detector	40	per piece	2500	100000	10 for each floorup to fourth floor
7	Smoke detector Accessoriesand installation charge	1	job	50000	50000	
8	Fire drills	1	job	100000	100000	expert fee, management, accessories fee
9	Awareness program	1	job	25000	25000	expert fee, management, accessories fee
10	Coordination with concerned authority	1	job	5000	5000	regular visit for firefighter, interaction
				Total	515000	

Amount in words: - Five lakh fifteen thousand Only

Note: - The above estimates are done on current market rate which may subject to change anytime. As mentioned it is a tentative estimate, so for exact estimate detail cost calculation should be done. Rates are collected from different website like (**Daraz.com and sastodeal.com**) and other rates are collected from expert and experience of researcher.

Table 4.12 Cost estimate For Hanuman central

S.no	Description	No	Unit	Rate	Quantity	Remarks
1	Exit Signs and boards(Digital)	20	per piece	2500	50000	
2	Overhead water tank forwater hydrant	1	L/s	250000	250000	for functioning of existing water tank on top floor
3	Fire Blanket	12	per piece	5000	60000	for 4 floor , at staircase i:e 3 staircase
4	Foam fire extinguisher	5	per piece	5000	25000	for each floor
5	Smoke detector	150	per piece	2500	375000	for each shop
6	Smoke detector Accessoriesand installation charge	1	job	10000	10000	
7	Fire drills	1	job	100000	100000	expert fee, management, accessories fee
8	Awareness program	1	job	25000	25000	expert fee, management, accessories fee
9	Coordination with concerned authority	1	job	5000	5000	regular visit for authority(Fire brigade)
10	Emergency alarm system	1	job	50000	50000	
				Total	950000	

Amount in words: - Nine lakh fifty thousand Only

Note: - The above estimates are done on current market rate which may subject to change anytime. As mentioned it is a tentative estimate, so for exact estimate detail cost calculation should be done. Rates are collected from different website like (**Daraz.com and sastodeal.com**) and other rates are collected from expert and experience of researcher.

CHAPTER-V: CONCLUSION AND RECOMENDATIONS

This study was conducted to check the current fire safety condition of existing commercial building, awareness and preparedness of management, concerned authority and occupant and to calculate the tentative cost of addition of fire safety in buildings. The objective of study was to check current fire safety condition. Study also focused on fire safety preparedness among the occupants, management and concerned authority and also to calculate the cost part in brief.

The source of primary data was questionnaire survey conducted with occupants of selected commercial buildings; Key informant interview and site visit with checklist. Whereas and secondary data were obtained from codes, literature review and research paper published. Based on the findings from research conclusion is derived.

5.1 Key Findings

Poor Fire safety condition

A general checklist for commercial building was prepared and current fire safety condition of building was checked. NBC 107: 1994 was also followed to check the safety of building. Only fire extinguishers and water hydrant system was found in Hanuman central. In one stop mall fire extinguisher, water hose reel, smoke detector, fire alarm system was also found. One stop mall seemed more prepared and safe in terms of fire safety as the exit way like (both side staircase and front escalator) was equidistance from every part of building. Staircase was narrow as compared to standard. Presence of International Standard QFX cinemas in the top of one stop mall has increased the fire safety measures in the building. In case of staircase one stop mall didn't met the NBC 107: 1994 guide line as it was narrow and steep.

Hanuman central has big atrium in the center of semi basement portion of building which will eventually help the occupants in semi basement floor for safe evacuation. Staircase seems wider and comfortable. Presence of three staircases at three side of the building seems more helpful for the occupants for safe evacuation in case of any emergency. There were 2 elevators but only was on working condition. On the both side of elevators there was 2 extinguishers. Water hydrant system was not in working condition but can be seen running vertically thorough all the staircase. Overhead tank was not installed for water hydrant. There was no any smoke detector and fire alarm. Management seems more focused on financial prospects of building. There was 25 number of fire extinguisher and more of them were dry powder. No any sign for exit was placed. Emergency number of firefighting was not placed anywhere in the building. There was no any emergency disaster kit placed in office.

1. Awareness and preparedness of Management, occupants and Concerned authority Awareness and preparedness of management of Hanuman central
 - ❖ Design of building seems to be more advanced and somewhat the fire preventive measures were followed but were incomplete.
 - ❖ No any seminar or awareness program for fire safety was ever conducted.
 - ❖ Due to more vacant space management seems more focused on renting the space rather than completing the water hydrant system and adding more fire safety features.
 - ❖ Water hydrant system was not in working condition as building is not completely occupied.
 - ❖ Exit at back is connected with staircase but that couldn't lead to open space.
 - Awareness of management of One stop Mall
 - ❖ Building is comparatively small and due to the presence of two staircases, two escalators and one elevator, emergency excavation seems easy for occupants.
 - ❖ Top Management seems more aware about the fire safety as management is planning to add more equipment's and conduct regular training and seminar regarding fire safety.
 - ❖ Power control room was at ground floor, secured and well ventilated.
 - ❖ Underground water tank was ready but not functional. Management was searching for technician who can complete the task.
2. Fire safety preparedness of occupants Awareness on feature of building
 - Awareness on building design was 37.5%.
 - Awareness on location of exit was 68.75%.
 - Visibility of emergency sign was 37.5%.

Awareness on emergency egress

 - Awareness on Emergency evacuation was 52.5 %.
 - Awareness on Assembly point was 32.5 %

Awareness on assistance

 - Need emergency assistance was 25%.
 - Assumption on provision of assistance was 18.75%. Awareness on existence of fire safety measure
 - Awareness on existence of fire extinguisher was 36.25%.
 - Awareness on existence of water reel hose was 27.5%.

Operation of fire safety measure

- Able to operate fire extinguisher was 28.75%.
 - Able to operate water reel hose was 8.75%.
3. There was a huge communication gap between all three parties. Municipality was weak in terms of fire safety code and by laws implementation. Management was more focused in financial aspects like renting empty space, collection of rent, etc. Due to the lack of proper education from school and community level, occupants were not prepared and aware about fire hazard and safety.

5.2 Conclusions

The current fire safety condition of building was found average. Fire safety tools and equipment's installed were seemed insufficient as compared to daily flow of occupants. The existed tools doesn't found in working condition. In case of staircase, staircase in Hanuman central is wider and seems to follow NBC 107:1994 detailing. Fire extinguisher was found in both building as the major equipment's fire safety. Management seems more focused on financial part of building (renting the empty space and collecting monthly rent). Smoke detector and fire alarm was found in "one stop mall only". Proper sign for emergency was not installed in both buildings. Hanuman central was designed with atrium but the smoke vent was not considered in the design.

All three parties (occupants, management, and concerned authorities) lacked awareness and preparedness. The residents of commercial buildings lacked fire safety knowledge and preparedness. They were uninformed about the building's general features, such as the floor plan and egress placement. In the same way, the residents were unaware of the assembly point and emergency evacuation method. They will also require aid in getting to a safe location. They were completely unaware of the building's safety features and were unable to use them. There was no proper fire safety management in existing commercial buildings, no fire drills were held, and inhabitants received no awareness or training. There was huge communication gap between all three parties. Management and occupants don't have direct communication (phone number) with fire brigade. In case of emergency people use to call Nepal police and Nepal police then call the fire fighter. The gap creates the delay for response. Also due to lack of new technology fire fighter finds hard to find the exact location. There was a problem for refilling the tank as there was no any fire hydrant installed by municipality. Fire fighters have to travel at least one kilometer to refill their tank. Due to unmanaged planning and narrow road fire fighter find hard to reach the location. There was no any coordination among the management, occupants and concerned authority.

Lack of fire expert in the Birtamode area was also a major problem for management to perform fire drills for occupants. The addition of fire safety tools and equipment's to the existing buildings seems less as compared to the loss that had occurred in the past due to fire

in the buildings. Also the weakness of Municipality in implementing fire safety codes and guidelines for the large commercial buildings was a major problem seen during study. Fire extinguisher and Firefighter from municipality seems to be only tool to fight in case of emergency.

5.3 Recommendation

Based on the conclusions, literature review, key informant interview and the results found from the case study, the following points can be recommended from researcher:

For Management

- The calculated cost of the addition of fire safety tools and equipment's seems less as compared to loss that might occur, so more fire safety tools and equipment's should be added as soon as possible.
- Fire drill and awareness program should be conducted frequently in coordination of concerned authority with the help from expert.
- The installed system (Water hydrant and water hose reels) should be made functional as soon as possible in both the buildings.
- Management should also focus on safety of occupants and put safety on top priority list.
- Different signs and boards should be installed for awareness of occupants. For occupants
- Occupants should always involve in safety program organized by authority and management.
- Occupants also should be aware about building features, fire safety tools and equipment's.
- Occupants should coordinate with the management for safe and healthy environment.

For concerned authority

- Fire safety code NBC 107:1994 should be strictly implemented.
- Municipality should develop their own guideline according to the geography and literacy.
- Municipality should organize site visit for firefighter to important commercial and public buildings.
- Municipality should strictly implement the fire safety code for newly registered buildings inside its area.
- The narrow road should be expanded as soon as possible.
- New technology should be introduced to firefighter so that they can find exact location, should organize regular training to the fire fighters.

- Municipality should organize regular awareness program and seminar using different media.
- Municipality should install fire hydrant in front of important commercial and public buildings.

5.4 Recommendation for further research work

Although the work done in this research represent contribution towards achieving the predefined objective set and to answer the research questions, numbers of issues were identified for future research.

- Construction and specification of fire resistance.
- Problems based on human behavior.
- Importance of fire safety for all the party.
- Cost of fire safety before and after the incidence.

REFERENCES

- Baker, J., 2013, *The Relationship Between Fire Damage And Fire Safety Management*, MPhil.Loughborough University.
- Craig, S.R., 2002, *Industrial Fire Protection Handbook*, 2nd Ed., Florida: CRC press LLC.
- Derek, J. 1986. *Fire Prevention Handbook*. London: Butterworth and Company (publishers) limited.
- Drabek, T. E. ,1986, *Human System Responses to Disaster*. New York: Springer-Verlag.
- Fire Safety: The Science and its Application to Building Codes*, Canada: NRC [Online]
Available at:<http://nparc.cisti-icist.nrc-cnrc.gc.ca/eng/view/fulltext/?id=a2f1e26c-8d11-4481-a1a2-4b9afd5478e8>[Accesses 24 July 2017].
- Furness, A., and Muckett, M., 2007, *Introduction to Fire Safety Management*, 1st ed.,UK Butterworth-Heinemann.
- Government of Nepal a, 1994, *Nepal National Building Code*, Kathmandu, Nepal, GoN.
Government of Nepal b, 2003, *Nepal National Building Code*, Kathmandu, Nepal, GoN.
- Ma, Q., Huangt,T., 2011. Analysis of and Study on the Difficulties in the Fire Protection Design of Large Commercial Complex. In: *Procedia Engineering, The 5th Conference on Performance-based Fire and Fire Protection Engineering*. Tianjin, China. Elsevier Ltd. [Online] Available at: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877705811008496> [Accesses 24 July].
- Madheshvani, [Online] Available at:
<http://madheshvani.com/en/details/1218/madhesh-news>[Accesses 24 July 2017].
- Malhotra, H. L.,1993, *Fire Safety in Buildings*, [Online]
Available at:<http://www.lmc.ep.usp.br/grupos/gsi/wp-content/artigos1/Malhotra.pdf> [Accesses 24 July 2017].
- Mehaffey , J. R., 1987, Flammability of building materials and fire growth, *Designing for Fire Safety: The Science and its Application to Building Codes*, Canada: NRC [Online]
Available at:<http://nparc.cisti-icist.nrc-cnrc.gc.ca/eng/view/fulltext/?id=a2f1e26c-8d11-4481-a1a2-4b9afd5478e8> [Accesses 24 July 2017].
- Moore, J. A., 2012, *Assessment of Fire Safety and Evacuation Management in Nursing Homes*. Mphil. Dublin Institute of Technology.
- Ogajo, N. J., 2013, *Influence of Fire Disasters on Mitigation And Preparedness in*

Commercial Premises in Kenya; A Survey Study Of Kisumu CBD. B.A. School of Built Environment, University Of Nairobi.

OSHA a, [Online] Available at:

https://www.osha.gov/OshDoc/data_General_Facts/emergency-exit-routes-factsheet.pdf [Accesses 24 July 2017].

OSHA b, [Online] Available at: <https://www.osha.gov/shppguidelines/hazard-prevention.html> [Accesses 24 July 2017].

Sagun, A., Anumba C. J., Bouchiaghem D., 2013, *Designing Buildings To Cope with Emergency: Finding From Case Studies On Exit Preferences*, pg 445.

Sun, Y., 2013, *Egress As Part of Fire Safety in High Rise Building*. Msc. Delft University of Technology.

Tzu-Sheng S., M.S., 2003, *Building Planning Evaluation for Emergency Evacuation*, PhD. Worcester Polytechnic Institute.

UNDP. 2009. *Recommendation for Update of Nepal National Building Code*. Kathmandu, Nepal: United Nation Development Program (UNDP).

Yatims, Y. M., 2009, *Fire Safety Models for High Rise Residential Building in Malaysia*. PhD. Edinburg: Herriot Watt University.

Assessment of Exit Requirements and Fire Safety Preparedness of Occupants of Selected Commercial Buildings (Mishra and Shrestha 2017)

<https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/PRR-12-2018-0033/full/html>

(https://www.firelab.org/sites/default/files/images/downloads/trip_report_nepal_april_2013_mchugh.pdf)

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320557369_Fire_Safety_Preparedness_among_Occupants_of_Selected_Commercial_Buildings_Kathmandu_Nepal

<https://fireandemergency.nz/business-and-landlords/fire-safety-regulatory-framework/>)

NBC 107:1994 (Provisional recommendation on fire safety) , NBC 206:2015 (Architectural Design Requirements)

APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Questionnaire for Fire Experts in Local Authority

1. Do you inspect buildings for fire safety compliance? Yes No

2. Do you carry out inspection and maintenance of firefighting equipment? Yes No
If yes, how often do you inspect
Weekly Monthly Yearly over one year

3. What do you think; do the commercial buildings have the necessary firefighting equipment?
Yes No

4. Were you satisfied with the available firefighting equipment? Yes No

5. Do you educate the owners/managers/occupants of commercial properties on fire safety? Yes No

6. Were you satisfied with the ability and capacity of your fire station to handle fire emergencies?
Yes No

7. In your opinion, what should be done to improve on fire preparedness and Mitigation strategies in buildings?

Appendix 2: Emergency Egress Questionnaire

Awareness of Building feature

1. Were you awareness of the part/nature/design of the building? Yes No Not sure
2. Were you awareness of location of the emergency exists in the building? Yes No Not sure
3. Were the signs which mark the emergency exits and others clear enough? Yes No Not sure

Awareness of Emergency Egress Procedures

4. Were you awareness of the emergency egress procedures that operate in of the building?
Yes No Not sure
5. Were you awareness of the assembly point in the building?
Yes No Not sure

Emergency Alarm

6. Do you the know fire alarm(s) provided in your place(s) of work?
Yes No Not sure
7. Could you raise the alarm if you discovered a fire?
Yes No Not sure

Assistance

8. Do you need assistance to get out of your place of work in an emergency?
Yes No Not sure
9. Do you think anyone designated to assist you to get out in an emergency?
Yes No Not sure

Fire safety Measures

10. Does fire extinguisher/dry chemical/dry powder extinguisher exit in the building?
Exit Do not exit Not sure
11. Does sprinkles/ water hose exit in the building? Exit Do not exit Not sure
12. Does fire hydrant exit in the building?
Exit Do not exit Not sure

Ability to operate fire equipment

13. Can you operate fire extinguisher/dry chemical/dry powder extinguisher?

Yes No Not sure

14. Can you operate sprinkles/ water hose?

Yes No Not sure

15. Can you operate fire hydrant exit in the building? YesNo Not sure

Appendix 3: Observation Chart

Observation Detail	Hanuman Central		One stop mall	
	Exist	Do not Exist	Exist	Do not Exist
Dry chemical extinguishers				
Halon extinguishers (vaporising liquids)				
Dry powder				
Carbon dioxide extinguishers				
Sprinklers/ Hose reels (pressurized water extinguishers)				
Wet chemical				
Fire blankets				
Emergency communication system (alarm, telephone, mobileno. etc)				
emergency shelters for this building				
Availability of an emergency fire disaster kit				
Existence of Emergency population warning methods				
Existence of a Fire hydrant				
Open spaces for evacuation of people				
Existence of a Fire Assembly point				

Appendix 4: Responses of Questionnaire by Occupants of Selected Commercial Building

	Hanuman Central(nos. of occupants)			One stop Mall (nos. of occupants)		
	Yes	No	Don'tknow	Yes	No	Don'tknow
Awwereeness on building feature						
Building plan						
Location of exit						
Visibility of emergency sign						
Awwereeness onemergency Egress						
Emergency evacuation						
Assembly point						
Awwereeness onFire Alarm						
Provision of alarm						
Raise for alarm						
Provision forassistance	Exit	Do notexit	Not sure	exit	Do notexit	Not sure
Need emergencyassistance						
Assistanceprovided						
Fire safetyMeasure	exit	Do not exit	Not sure	exit	Do not exit	Not sure
Fire extinguisher						
Water hose reel						
Fire hydrant						
Ability To Operate Fire Equipment	Ableto	Notable to	Not sure	Able to	Notable to	Not sure
Fire extinguisher						
Sprinkles/hose reel						
Fire hydrant						

Appendix 5: Responses of Questionnaire by Management of One Stop Mall

Q. No. 1) What are the system that you have installed for firefighting?

Ans :- We have 25 fire extinguisher, fire alarm system in top floor, Smoke Detector, fire resistant material installed inside the Cinema Hall, water hose reel on both the staircase.

Q. No 2) Are all them are in working condition?

Ans :- Yes, except the water hose reel as underground tank isn't ready yet for operation.

Q. No 3) Can you describe your building in case of fire safety?

Ans: - Our building is designed in such a way that both staircase and escalators and elevators are not more than 20 m far from any point of building. Due to the presence of four exit emergency evacuation will be in case of emergency.

Q. No 4) Staircase seems narrow, what is the reason behind that?

Ans: - It was due to miscommunication between consultant and contractor.

Q. No 5) Have you assigned any person as fire expert of building?

Ans :- Security guards and manger of building are assigned the role. But due to frequent change of security personnel it is hard to train them in regular basis.

Q. No 6) Have you organized any awareness and fire drill in this building?

Ans :- No, not yet. There are no any experts near and also it is hard to find expert.

Q. No 7) Are you aware of risk of fire in Buildings?

Ans :- Yes, we want to conduct a fire drill and organize a awareness program as soon as possible. We have kept the power room safe and properly ventilated. We have requested Municipality to install fire hydrant near our building. All the extinguishers are up to date.

Q. No 8) Are you satisfied with the system installed in your building?

Ans :- No, We want install smoke detector throughout the building but due to the lack awareness among the occupants and also it is almost impossible to make a building smoking free zone so we cannot install it. As the building is not fully operated now due to Pandemic, we will organize awareness program and perform fire drill as soon as possible. We will try more to install fire hydrant that have water supply 24/7 in case of emergency. We will install more fire safety sign in building.

Appendix 6: Responses of Questionnaire by Management of Hanuman Central

Q. No. 1) What are the system that you have installed for firefighting?

Ans :- We have 40 fire extinguisher, water hydrant system on all three of the staircase.

Q. No 2) Are all them are in working condition?

Ans :- Yes, except the water hydrant as overhead tank isn't ready yet for operation.

Q. No 3) Can you describe your building in case of fire safety?

Ans :- Our building is designed in such a way that all three staircase and both are not more than 20 m far from any point of building. Due to the presence of four exits emergency evacuation will be in case of emergency. Due to atrium in the middle of the building the emergency evacuation is easy and flow of people is easy.

Q. No 4) Have you assigned any person as fire expert of building?

Ans :- Security guards and manger of building are assigned the role. Banks have their own fire expert.

Q. No 5) Have you organized any awareness and fire drill in this building?

Ans :- No, not yet. There are no any experts near and also it is hard to find expert.

Q. No 6) As previously there was fire case here, are you aware of risk of fire in Buildings?

Ans :- Yes, we want to conduct a fire drill and organize awareness program as soon as possible. We have kept the power room safe and properly ventilated. All the extinguishers are up to date. As previously there was fire due to electrical hazard, we inspect regularly electricalsystem.

Q. No 7) Are you satisfied with the system installed in your building?

Ans :- No, We want install smoke detector throughout the building but due to the lack awareness among the occupants and also it is almost impossible to make a building smoking free zone so we cannot install it. As the building is not fully operated now due to Pandemic and also the top floor of building is not occupied yet, we will organize awareness program andperform fire drill as soon as possible. We will try more to install fire hydrant that have water supply 24/7 in case of emergency. We will install more fire safety sign in building. We will construct overhead tank for water hydrants as soon as possible.

Appendix 7: Responses of Questionnaire by Fire Brigade Birtamode Municipality.

Q. No. 1) Are you aware of the building feature?

Ans: - No

Q. No 2) Have there been any program that connects firefighting team with building feature?

Ans: - No

Q. No 3) what were the difficulty you faced during fire in Hanuman Central?

Ans: - Lack of direct communication was major problem as people first connect to Nepal police and then Nepal police directed them towards us. Due to the public interfere firefighting became difficult. Lack of source of was another problem as there was no fire hydrant and we have to travel up to 2km for water. Water hydrant system was not in working condition so we have to depend on totally our resources.

Q. No 4) How often there is a training and seminar?

Ans :- Very few, training has been done through virtual method using projector so it is hard for us practically to perform.

Q. No 5) what are the resources available?

Ans :- One fire engine and one water tanker.

Q. No 6) What are the Steps that should be implemented to improve for proper response to fire in Municipality?

Ans :- Steps that should be taken to improve are

1. Strict implementation of code and bylaws.
2. Regular fire safety awareness program and campaign.
3. Fire safety training to the new owner.
4. Regular visit to the public and commercial building.
5. Addition of advance technology to the fire fighter.
6. Establishment of direct communication system from people to firefighter.
7. Expansion of existing narrow road.